

=====

Public Sector Management Education in the Philippines for 21st Century Governance: Challenges, Strategies, and Innovation

=====

Mary Ann B. Parinasan

Teacher III, Sirao Integrated School, Tawagan, Sirao, Cebu City, Philippines
Graduate School of Education Student, University of the Visayas, Colon St. Cebu City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7562-562X> | maryann.parinasan@deped.gov.ph

Misty Marie R. Rosal

SHS Teacher II, Bulacao National High School, Cabancalan 1, Bulacao, Cebu City, Philippines
Xxx | mistymarie.rosal@deped.gov.ph

Osias Kit T. Kilag

Principal, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Mercado St., Poblacion, Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0845-3373> | okkilag@excellencia.edu.ph

Coenrad Adolph Groenewald

Consulting Director, SG Virtuosos International, Cape Town, South Africa
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2394-6347> | dolfgroenewald@sgvirtuososinternational.com

Elma S. Groenewald

CEO, SG Virtuosos International, Loc Tho Ward, Nha Trang City, Khanh Hoa Province, Vietnam
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7813-2773> | elmasgroenewald@sgvirtuososinternational.com

Paul Marie L. Gepitulan

Teacher, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Mercado St., Poblacion, Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3232-2971> | paulmariegepitulan@gmail.com

Abstract:

This systematic literature review examines the state of public sector management education in the Philippines and proposes strategies for its enhancement to meet 21st-century needs. Findings reveal a diverse array of educational programs offered by various institutions, yet challenges persist in aligning education with contemporary demands. These challenges include a gap between theory and practice, limited resources for faculty development, and a reluctance to embrace emerging trends like digital transformation. However, promising strategies emerge, such as fostering partnerships with government agencies, promoting interdisciplinary approaches, integrating experiential learning, and leveraging information technologies. Embracing these strategies is crucial for equipping future public sector leaders with the skills and knowledge necessary to navigate complex governance challenges. Continuous adaptation and innovation are paramount, requiring collaboration between curriculum developers, policymakers, and stakeholders to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education in the Philippines.

Keywords: public sector management education, Philippines, 21st century, curriculum development

Introduction:

In the Philippines, as in many countries across the globe, the public sector plays a pivotal role in driving socio-economic development, ensuring good governance, and delivering essential services to citizens. As we navigate through the complexities of the 21st century, characterized by rapid technological advancements, globalization, and evolving societal demands, the need for an adept and forward-thinking public sector becomes increasingly evident. Consequently, the education and training of public sector managers emerge as critical components in ensuring the efficacy and responsiveness of governmental institutions.

The evolution of public sector management education mirrors the shifting paradigms within governance and administration. Traditional models of public administration, emphasizing hierarchical structures and bureaucratic processes, have gradually given way to more flexible, collaborative, and innovation-oriented approaches. Scholars such as Hood (1991) have highlighted the importance of "new public management" principles, advocating for managerial autonomy, performance measurement, and market-like mechanisms in public service delivery. Furthermore, the advent of digital technologies has prompted discussions on "e-government" and the potential for leveraging information and communication technologies (ICTs) to enhance governmental operations (Moon, 2002).

However, despite these advancements, the landscape of public sector management education in the Philippines often faces challenges in keeping pace with the dynamic demands of the 21st century. While there have been efforts to integrate modern management concepts into academic curricula, there remains a gap between theory

and practice, and a need for continuous adaptation to emerging trends (Bouckaert & Jann, 2020). Additionally, factors such as limited resources, institutional inertia, and resistance to change can impede the reform process (Hood, 1995).

This study seeks to address these gaps by examining the current state of public sector management education in the Philippines and proposing strategies for curriculum development that align with the needs of the 21st century. By synthesizing insights from academic literature, policy documents, and interviews with key stakeholders, the researchers aim to identify areas for improvement and recommend actionable steps towards enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education. Ultimately, our research endeavors to contribute to the capacity-building efforts necessary for nurturing a cadre of public sector leaders capable of navigating the complexities of contemporary governance and driving sustainable development in the Philippines.

Literature Review:

The literature surrounding public sector management education provides valuable insights into the evolving paradigms, challenges, and strategies pertinent to the preparation of government leaders and administrators. This literature review aims to synthesize existing scholarship, focusing on the context of the Philippines, to inform the development of a responsive curriculum tailored to the demands of the 21st century.

The evolution of public sector management education reflects broader shifts in governance theory and practice. Traditional approaches, rooted in principles of hierarchical bureaucracy, have gradually been supplanted by more contemporary models emphasizing flexibility, responsiveness, and innovation (Hood, 1991). In the Philippines, this transition has been influenced by factors such as globalization, technological advancement, and democratization (Guinigundo, 2018).

Despite progress, public sector management education in the Philippines faces several challenges. These include a gap between academic theory and practical application, limited resources for faculty development and research, and a lack of alignment with the dynamic needs of the public sector (Alvarez Jr, 2020). Moreover, issues such as bureaucratic inertia and resistance to change within educational institutions can impede curriculum reform efforts (Jónasson, 2016).

Relevance of New Public Management:

The principles of New Public Management (NPM) have significantly influenced public sector management education globally. NPM advocates for managerial autonomy, performance-based incentives, and market-oriented reforms (Hood, 1995). While NPM has been critiqued for its emphasis on efficiency over equity and its potential to exacerbate social inequalities (Park, 2022), its principles continue to inform curriculum design and pedagogical approaches in the Philippines.

The integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) presents both opportunities and challenges for public sector management education. ICTs have the potential to enhance administrative efficiency, facilitate transparency, and improve service delivery (Moon, 2002). However, the digital divide, inadequate ICT infrastructure, and cybersecurity concerns pose obstacles to leveraging ICTs effectively in the Philippine context (Espinosa, et al., 2023).

International Perspectives on Public Sector Management Education:

Comparative studies offer valuable insights into alternative models of public sector management education. Cross-national analyses highlight variations in curriculum content, pedagogical approaches, and institutional arrangements (Niedlich, 2021). Learning from international best practices can inform curriculum development efforts in the Philippines, fostering a more global outlook among future public sector leaders.

Several strategies have been proposed to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education in the Philippines. These include strengthening partnerships between academia and government agencies, promoting interdisciplinary approaches, incorporating experiential learning opportunities, and leveraging ICTs for interactive and participatory learning (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2016).

The literature reviewed underscores the importance of continuously adapting public sector management education to meet the evolving needs of the 21st century. By addressing challenges such as the gap between theory and practice, limited resources, and resistance to change, curriculum developers can cultivate a cadre of government leaders equipped to navigate complex governance challenges and drive sustainable development in the Philippines.

Methodology:

A systematic literature review was conducted to synthesize existing scholarship relevant to the research topic of gearing public sector management education in the Philippines to meet 21st-century needs. The review process followed established guidelines for systematic literature reviews, including the identification of research questions,

search strategy development, study selection criteria, data extraction, and analysis (Tranfield, Denyer, & Smart, 2003).

A comprehensive search strategy was developed to identify relevant literature. Electronic databases including PubMed, Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Scopus were searched using combinations of keywords such as "public sector management education," "Philippines," "curriculum development," "21st century," and related terms. Additionally, manual searches of key journals and reference lists of relevant articles were conducted to ensure thorough coverage of the literature.

Relevant data from selected studies were systematically extracted, including author(s), publication year, research methods, key findings, and implications for public sector management education.

Data synthesis involved organizing extracted information into thematic categories related to key themes, challenges, opportunities, and strategies identified in the literature. Patterns, similarities, and discrepancies across studies were analyzed to provide a comprehensive overview of the state of public sector management education in the Philippines. The quality of included studies was assessed using criteria appropriate to their respective research designs (e.g., qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods). Studies were evaluated based on methodological rigor, relevance to the research questions, and contribution to the overall understanding of the topic.

Findings and Discussion:

Current State of Public Sector Management Education in the Philippines:

The systematic literature review illuminates the current landscape of public sector management education in the Philippines, showcasing a rich tapestry of programs offered by diverse academic institutions. Carrizales & Gaynor (2013) underscore this diversity, highlighting a broad spectrum of subjects covered in these programs, including public administration, policy analysis, financial management, and governance. This comprehensive approach reflects the multifaceted nature of public sector management, recognizing the need for interdisciplinary knowledge and skills to navigate the complexities of contemporary governance challenges. Such breadth in educational offerings indicates a recognition among academic institutions of the varied demands placed on public sector professionals, from policy formulation to implementation and evaluation.

Institutional offerings in public sector management education cater to a wide range of learners, including aspiring government officials, civil servants, and public policy analysts. These programs often adopt a mix of theoretical foundations and practical applications, aiming to equip students with both conceptual frameworks and hands-on experience relevant to public service contexts. The diverse array of topics covered in these programs reflects an effort to address the multifaceted challenges encountered by public sector professionals in their day-to-day work (Kozlowski & Ilgen, 2006).

Furthermore, the presence of various academic institutions offering public sector management education speaks to the recognition of the importance of cultivating a skilled and knowledgeable workforce capable of driving effective governance and public service delivery in the Philippines. As highlighted by Kozlowski, S. W., & Ilgen (2006), these educational initiatives play a vital role in nurturing a cadre of public sector leaders equipped to address the complex socio-economic and political issues facing the country. By providing students with a robust foundation in public administration principles, policy analysis techniques, financial management practices, and governance frameworks, these programs contribute to the professionalization and capacity-building of the public sector workforce.

The literature underscores the significance of public sector management education in the Philippines as a means of preparing future leaders and administrators to tackle the challenges of governance in the 21st century. Through a diverse array of educational offerings spanning various disciplines, academic institutions strive to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to navigate the intricacies of public service and contribute to the advancement of the nation.

Challenges in Aligning Education with 21st-Century Needs:

The systematic examination of literature exposes significant hurdles impeding the synchronization of public sector management education with the demands of the 21st century. Welch IV (2017) delineates these challenges, pinpointing a disjunction between theoretical constructs and real-world application as a primary obstacle. This gap between academic theory and practical implementation undermines the efficacy of educational endeavors, leaving graduates ill-prepared to address contemporary governance complexities.

Moreover, the review underscores the issue of limited resources allocated to faculty development and research within public sector management education. Lodge (2018) elucidates on this challenge, highlighting the detrimental impact on the quality and relevance of educational programs. Insufficient investment in faculty development hampers the ability of educators to stay abreast of evolving trends and innovative methodologies, perpetuating a cycle of stagnation in curriculum design and delivery.

Furthermore, the literature illuminates a concerning lack of responsiveness to emergent trends such as digital transformation and globalization within public sector management education. Ulanday, et al. (2022) emphasizes the need for educational institutions to adapt swiftly to these transformative forces, equipping students with the requisite skills and competencies to navigate a rapidly evolving landscape. Failure to integrate these contemporary themes into the curriculum risks rendering public sector management education obsolete and disconnected from the realities of modern governance (Uy, et al., 2023).

The review underscores the multifaceted challenges facing the alignment of public sector management education with 21st-century imperatives. These obstacles encompass a disparity between theory and practice, resource constraints in faculty development, and a reluctance to embrace emerging trends (Orozco, et al., 2023). Addressing these challenges is imperative to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education in equipping future leaders with the skills needed to navigate the complexities of contemporary governance.

Strategies for Enhancing Relevance and Effectiveness:

The literature review unveils a spectrum of strategies aimed at augmenting the relevance and efficacy of public sector management education in the Philippines, notwithstanding prevailing challenges Thomas (2012), as well as Wali, et al. (2023), shed light on these strategies, emphasizing their potential to address the pressing needs of contemporary governance.

One pivotal strategy involves fostering robust partnerships between academia and government agencies. By forging collaborative ties, educational institutions can gain valuable insights into the practical realities of public service, thus ensuring the alignment of curricula with current needs and challenges (Thomas, 2012).

Additionally, the literature underscores the importance of adopting interdisciplinary approaches within public sector management education. Darling-Hammond, et al. (2020) highlights the efficacy of integrating diverse disciplinary perspectives, such as economics, sociology, and public policy, in enhancing students' understanding of complex governance issues and fostering innovative problem-solving skills (Martinez, et al., 2023).

Moreover, the incorporation of experiential learning opportunities emerges as a key strategy for enriching the educational experience (Noble, et al., 2023). By providing students with hands-on exposure to real-world challenges, such as internships, fieldwork, and case studies, educational institutions can bridge the gap between theory and practice, thus equipping graduates with practical skills and competencies essential for effective public service (Allsopp, et al., 2006).

Furthermore, leveraging information and communication technologies (ICTs) holds immense potential for enhancing the interactive and participatory nature of public sector management education. Seenivasan (2024) underscores the transformative impact of ICTs in facilitating collaborative learning environments, enabling virtual simulations, and fostering peer-to-peer engagement among students.

The literature illuminates a plethora of strategies aimed at bolstering the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education in the Philippines. Through partnerships with government agencies, interdisciplinary approaches, experiential learning opportunities, and the integration of ICTs, educational institutions can navigate the challenges of contemporary governance and cultivate a cadre of adept public sector leaders poised to address 21st-century challenges.

Need for Continuous Adaptation and Innovation:

The literature review underscores the imperative for continuous adaptation and innovation in public sector management education to effectively address the dynamic demands of the 21st century. Gouédard, et al. (2020) highlight this necessity, emphasizing the pivotal role of curriculum developers and policymakers in steering educational reform efforts towards responsiveness and relevance.

In the face of rapid societal, technological, and economic changes, public sector management education must evolve to equip future leaders with the skills and competencies essential for navigating complex governance challenges (Aquino, et al., 2023). This requires a proactive approach from educational institutions and policymakers, who must remain attuned to emerging trends and responsive to evolving needs (Darling-Hammond, et al., 2020).

Curriculum developers play a central role in this process, tasked with designing and updating educational programs to reflect contemporary realities and equip students with the requisite knowledge and skills. By integrating innovative pedagogical approaches, interdisciplinary content, and experiential learning opportunities, educational institutions can foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability among students (Allsopp, et al., 2006).

Moreover, policymakers must provide the necessary support and resources to facilitate educational reform initiatives. This includes investing in faculty development, promoting collaboration between academia and government agencies, and leveraging technology to enhance the educational experience (Tanaka & Lopez, 2024).

By fostering an enabling environment for innovation and collaboration, policymakers can contribute to the continuous improvement of public sector management education in the Philippines.

Embracing emerging trends such as digital transformation, globalization, and sustainable development is essential for ensuring the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education. By incorporating these themes into the curriculum and fostering a culture of lifelong learning, educational institutions can prepare students to address pressing societal challenges and drive positive change in their respective roles as public sector leaders and administrators (Mulford, 2003). By embracing change, addressing challenges, and leveraging opportunities, curriculum developers and policymakers can cultivate a cadre of government leaders equipped to navigate the complexities of contemporary governance and drive sustainable development in the 21st century.

Conclusion:

The systematic literature review sheds light on the intricacies of public sector management education in the Philippines and illuminates pathways for its enhancement to meet the demands of the 21st century. The findings underscore the diversity of educational programs offered by various institutions, reflecting an acknowledgment of the multifaceted challenges faced by public sector professionals. However, challenges persist, including the gap between theory and practice, resource constraints, and a reluctance to embrace emerging trends such as digital transformation and globalization.

Nevertheless, the literature reveals promising strategies for enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of public sector management education. These strategies include fostering partnerships between academia and government agencies, promoting interdisciplinary approaches, incorporating experiential learning opportunities, and leveraging information and communication technologies. By embracing innovation and collaboration, curriculum developers and policymakers can cultivate a cadre of government leaders equipped to navigate the complexities of contemporary governance and drive sustainable development.

Thus, it is imperative for stakeholders in public sector management education to prioritize continuous adaptation and innovation. Curriculum developers must remain vigilant in updating educational programs to reflect evolving needs and emerging trends, while policymakers must provide the necessary support and resources to facilitate educational reform initiatives. By embracing change, addressing challenges, and seizing opportunities, the Philippines can strengthen its public sector management education system and nurture a generation of adept leaders capable of tackling the pressing challenges of the 21st century.

References:

- Allsopp, D. H., DeMarie, D., Alvarez-McHatton, P., & Doone, E. (2006). Bridging the gap between theory and practice: Connecting courses with field experiences. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 33(1), 19-35.
- Alvarez Jr, A. V. (2020). Learning from the Problems and Challenges in Blended Learning: Basis for Faculty Development and Program Enhancement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 112-132.
- Aquino, S. R., Kilag, O. K., & Valle, J. (2023). From Preparedness to Action: Effective Real-time Crisis Management. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(5), 372-384.
- Bouckaert, G., & Jann, W. (2020). *European perspectives for public administration: The way forward* (p. 468). Leuven University Press.
- Carrizales, T., & Gaynor, T. S. (2013). Diversity in public administration research: A review of journal publications. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 306-330.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied developmental science*, 24(2), 97-140.
- Espinosa, A. A., Gomez, M. A. C., Miranda, P. A., David, A. P., Abulon, E. L. R., Hermosisima, M. V. C., ... & Gonzales, N. S. (2023). Technology in education: a case study on the Philippines.
- Gouëdard, P., Pont, B., Hyttinen, S., & Huang, P. (2020). Curriculum reform: A literature review to support effective implementation.
- Guinigundo, D. C. (2018). The globalisation experience and its challenges for the Philippine economy. *BIS Paper*, (100q).
- Hood, C. (1991). A public management for all seasons?. *Public administration*, 69(1), 3-19.

- Hood, C. (1995). The "new public management" in the 1980s: Variations on a theme. *Accounting, organizations and society*, 20(2-3), 93-109.
- Jónasson, J. T. (2016). Educational change, inertia and potential futures. *European Journal of Futures Research*, 4(1), 1-14.
- Kozlowski, S. W., & Ilgen, D. R. (2006). Enhancing the effectiveness of work groups and teams. *Psychological science in the public interest*, 7(3), 77-124.
- Lodge, J. M., Kennedy, G., Lockyer, L., Arguel, A., & Pachman, M. (2018, June). Understanding difficulties and resulting confusion in learning: An integrative review. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 3, p. 49). Frontiers Media SA.
- Martinez, N., Kilag, O. K., & Macario, R. (2023). The Impact of Organizational Culture on Leadership Strategies in Crisis Management. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(5), 454-466.
- Moon, M. J. (2002). The evolution of e-government among municipalities: rhetoric or reality?. *Public administration review*, 62(4), 424-433.
- Mulford, B. (2003). School leaders: Challenging roles and impact on teacher and school effectiveness. *a paper prepared for the OECD Improving School Leadership activity, available at www.oecd.org/edu/schoolleadership*.
- Niedlich, S. (2021). Cross-national Analysis of Education and Trust: Context, Comparability, and Causal Mechanisms. *European Education*, 53(3-4), 181-202.
- Noble, J. I., Kilag, O. K., & Viscara, C. (2023). Bridging Academia and Community: A Holistic Approach to Disaster Risk Management. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(6), 36-45.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2016). *Innovating education and educating for innovation: The power of digital technologies and skills*. OECD.
- Orozco, F., Kilag, O. K., & Parinasan, M. A. (2023). Navigating Unpredictability: Exploring Fundamental Components of Crisis Management in Organizational Settings. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(6), 1-11.
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., ... & Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *International journal of surgery*, 88, 105906.
- Park, S. (2022). The Construction of Social Inequity and the Role of Public Bureaucracies. *Journal of Policy Studies*, 4(37), 1-15.
- Seenivasan, R. (2024). ICT in Education: A Critical Literature Review and Its Implications. *International Journal of Finance, Insurance and Risk Management*, 14(1), 12-27.
- Thomas, G. W. (2012). Governance, good governance, and global governance: conceptual and actual challenges. In *Thinking about global governance* (pp. 168-189). Routledge.
- Tanaka, M. L., & Lopez, O. (2024). Outlook on Industry-Academia-Government Collaborations Impacting Medical Device Innovation. *Journal of Engineering and Science in Medical Diagnostics and Therapy*, 7(2).
- Tranfield, D., Denyer, D., & Smart, P. (2003). Towards a methodology for developing evidence-informed management knowledge by means of systematic review. *British journal of management*, 14(3), 207-222.
- Ulanday, M. L., Centeno, Z. J., Bayla, M. C., & Callanta, J. (2021). Flexible learning adaptabilities in the new normal: E-learning resources, digital meeting platforms, online learning systems and learning engagement. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 16(2).
- Uy, F., Kilag, O. K., Abendan, C. F., Macapobre, K., Cañizares, M. C., & Yray, F. (2023). Application of Adaptive Crisis Management Theory: The Dynamics of Leadership in Times of Crisis. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(5), 159-170.
- Wali, K., van Paridon, K., & Darwish, B. K. (2023). Strengthening banking sector governance: challenges and solutions. *Future Business Journal*, 9(1), 95.
- Welch IV, J. (2017). All Too Human: Conflict and Common Ground in Interdisciplinary Research and Complex Problem Solving. *Issues in interdisciplinary studies*, 35, 88-112.